

Original Research

Does Bank Size Matter on Performance and Liquidity Risk Management? Evidence From Commercial Banks in Tanzania

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Abstract

This study examines the relationship between risk management and performance based on the size of commercial banks in Tanzania. Specifically, the study aims to determine the effect of liquid asset/Total asset ratio on Return on asset (ROA). Data employed were extracted from audited financial statement report. The explanatory variables were liquid asset/Total asset ratio while the dependent variable was financial performance measured by return on asset. Panel data of 23 commercial banks for the period of five years (2017 to 2021) was employed. Fixed and random model was adopted in analyzing the data. Findings highlight that the impact of liquid asset/Total asset on performance varies among commercial banks, with large banks showing insignificant positive relationship, while medium and small banks exhibit weak but significant negative relationship. This implies that maintaining more liquid assets compared to total assets provides a certain level of risk management capability though it may lead to relatively small returns to small and medium commercial banks. As far as large banks are concerned the relationship does not lead low return. Therefore, the study recommends that banks should establish optimal size of liquidity to maximize returns and invest excess liquidity in higher-yielding assets or where additional income can be generated without significantly increasing risk. Regulatory authorities may need to consider different liquidity risk management policies depending on the size of the bank, such as tailoring the policies to ensure that the proportion of liquid assets is appropriate and reflect size of the bank. Consequently, it may help small banks and medium avoid excessive liquid assets which can negatively impact their financial performance.

Keywords: Commercial bank, financial performance, liquidity risk.

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Introduction

Liquidity risk in commercial banks refers to the risk to a bank's earnings or capital due to its inability to meet its obligations as they fall due (Muriithi & Waweru, 2017). This concept gained prominence during the global economic crisis of 2008-2010, which led to the collapse of financial systems worldwide, with liquidity being identified as a key contributing factor (Vodová, 2011). The crisis exposed the vulnerability to many financial firms due to their inadequate management of liquidity, emphasizing the critical role of liquidity in the proper functioning of the financial system (Sidhu et al., 2022). The sudden changes in market conditions highlighted how rapidly liquidity could disappear, leaving firms grappling with the challenge of selling assets at values significantly lower than market rates or borrowing at interest rates exceeding their weighted return on assets (Marozva, 2015).

Efficient liquidity management is essential and involves maintaining adequate cash reserves while strategically investing excess funds to optimize earnings. A bank's ability to fulfill its commitments promptly and without delay significantly influences its overall financial performance. Commercial banks, as key players in the allocation of economic resources across nations, play a crucial role in this vital process. More than 70 percent of the financial sector is accounted for by the banking sector, commercial banks account for more than 73 percent of banking institutions (BOT, 2021). The financial performance of banks has a significant impact on a country's economic growth. Since profitability and stability of the bank are both at risk if its liquidity is inadequate. Loans, advances, and overdrafts made up 50.87 percent of the Tanzania banking sector's assets in 2017 and increased up to 56.2 percent in 2021, leaving these institutions particularly vulnerable to risks, including liquidity risk. Despite the banking sector as a whole has kept its ratio of liquid assets to demand liabilities at a level higher than the BOT's minimum requirement of 20%. As time went on, the liquidity ratio dropped from 40.27 percent in 2017 to 35.22 percent in 2018, 32.14 percent in 2019 to 30.72 percent in 2020, and 29.4 percent in 2021. According to the Bank of Tanzania, the drop in the liquidity ratio can be explained by a move into higher-yielding investments including loans, advances, and overdrafts as well as debt securities which expose banking sector to liquidity risk. Liquidity difficulties may negatively impact a bank's financial performance and solvency (Mwangi, 2021).

Several financial institutions have resorted to self-discipline by creating predefined policies on loan provisions and cash on hand, in addition to the mandatory prudential standards (Akhtar & Saleem, 2021). Theoretically speaking, there has been a great need to maintain appropriate liquidity levels, and this has directly influenced long-term performance (Amnim et al., 2021). However, there needs shift away from theorizing and consider figuring out the facts that support the theories. As therefore, it is critical to analyse how liquidity risk management affects banks' profitability based on the banks size (small, medium and large) in Tanzania. Specifically, the study aims to determine the influence of liquid asset/total asset on the return on asset based on the banks' size.

Statement of the Problem

In the vital process of allocating economic resources across nations, commercial banks play a significant role. Continuously channeling cash from depositors to investors is one

of their primary functions. Tanzania's financial sector includes the banking industry, social security systems, insurance markets, stock exchanges, and microfinance institutions. More than 70 percent of the financial sector is accounted for by the banking sector. Banking institutions include commercial banks, development finance banks, community banks, and microfinance banks. Commercial banks account for more than 73 percent of banking institutions (BOT, 2021). A bank's profitability and stability are both at risk if its liquidity is inadequate. Loans, advances, and overdrafts made up 50.87 percent of the Tanzania banking sector's assets in 2017 and increased up to 56.2 percent in 2021, leaving these institutions particularly vulnerable to risks, including liquidity risk.

Referring to prior research, the results regarding liquidity are varying. Some studies have demonstrated a strong correlation between bank profits and liquidity, while others have demonstrated no correlation. Bordeleau & Graham, (2010) suggested that there is nonlinear relationship between profitability of banks and liquid assets that banks do maintain. However, beyond a certain point, holding additional liquid assets decreases a bank's profitability, all factors being equal. Chen, Y-K, et al., (2018) discovered that the result for liquidity's effect on profitability is inconclusive and not statistically significant, indicating that the conclusion regarding liquidity's influence remains questionable and more research is required.

Several financial institutions have resorted to self-discipline by creating predefined policies on loan provisions and cash on hand, in addition to the mandatory prudential standards. Theoretically speaking, there has been a great need to maintain appropriate liquidity levels, and this has directly influenced long-term performance as well as stability. However, there needs to be a shift away from theorizing and towards figuring out the facts that support the theories. Therefore, it is critical to analyze how liquidity risk affects banks' profitability in Tanzania based on size of commercial bank. Several studies have been conducted on the relationship between the liquidity risk and financial performance of commercial banks. however, little attention has been given to the same relationship based on the bank size. Therefore, specific objectives of this research objective of this study focusses on how does bank size affect the liquidity risk management practices of commercial banks in Tanzania. The remaining sections of the paper covers the following; *section two* covers literature (both theoretical and empirical) of previous similar studies conducted on the same topic. *Section three* covers techniques used in this study, this includes data and variables used as well as the methods and model used in the analysis. Findings and discussion of the results are presented in *section four* while *section five* covers the conclusion, limitations of this study as well as recommended areas for future studies.

Literature Review

Empirical Review

The relationship between liquidity risk and a bank's performance is intricate and multifaceted, with conflicting findings in empirical research. Some studies suggest that greater liquidity risk is associated with a reduction in a bank's performance. However, the literature reveals diverse perspectives, including positive, negative, both positive and negative, or no clear relationship at all.

Conflicting views persist regarding the impact of increased liquidity risk on a bank's performance, and it remains unclear. Studies examining bank performance in specific regions, such as Africa and Europe, often focus on a single country and employ variables like Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE). Some researchers, such as Ajibike & Aremu (2015), Alshatti (2015), Sayedi, (2014), (Siaw, 2013), Goddard et al. (2004), Kosmidou et al. (2005), Poposka & Trpkoski, (2013) argue that increased liquidity risk can enhance banks' performance. Gafrej & Boujelbéne (2022). Carried out a study on the relationship between liquidity and credit risk on the bank diversification as the means of managing risks. The study was done in Gulf countries between 2006-2018, including 66 Gulf countries. Their findings revealed existence of the relationship between liquidity risks and diversification as risk management strategies.

Al-Ardah & Al-Okdeh, (2022) conducted a study on the effect of liquidity risks on banks performance in Jordan using 13 commercial banks from 2010 to 2019. Findings revealed that there was an impact of liquidity risks on the performance of the Jordanian commercial banks. Findings further confirm that size of the banks is relevant in modifying the impact of the liquidity risks on financial performance measured by return on assets. In Pakistan, the effect of liquidity risk management on financial performance of commercial banks was examined between 2009 to 2019. Ordinary least square was used and findings revealed that higher liquidity in commercial banks increase banks' performance (Alim et al., 2021).

On the other hand, research conducted in Asia by Lee & Kim (2013), in Europe by Ndoka et al. (2017), and in Africa by Basse & Moses (2015) and Kutsienyo (2011) suggests that liquidity risk negatively affects bank performance. These studies also primarily employ ROA and ROE as variables to define and measure bank performance. The varying results underscore the complexity of the relationship between liquidity risk and bank performance and highlight the need for further comprehensive research in this domain. On top of that, depending on the research model used, several studies, including a number of examples in Asia, show either no relationship between liquidity risk and bank performance or a correlation Sufian & Chong (2008). Researchers in the Americas Anbar & Alper, (2011); Bordeleau & Graham, (2010); DeYoung & Jang, (2016); Ferrouhi, (2014) found that liquidity risk did not significantly affect bank performance. Bordeleau & Graham (2010) Banks can enhance their earnings by holding liquid assets, but eventually their performance was suffer as a result of doing so .

On the other hand, these have not completely utilized all of the elements that influence bank performance and the liquidity risk measuring indicator. Empirical studies suggest that the performance of a bank is affected by a number of elements that are inherent to the organization itself. These factors include the bank's size, asset quality, and ownership Sidhu et al. (2022). However, few of the previous studies investigated this aspect of the problem. This study used a more holistic approach to investigate this question of how the influence of liquidity risk has on the financial performance of commercial banks in Tanzania in an effort to fill in the research gaps that have been identified above. The research goes a step further by exploring how this link shifts when bank-specific criteria such as size are introduced (concentrating on peer bank groupings according to Ernst & Young (2021). It is essential and beneficial to use a combination of methods for

evaluating the influence of liquidity risk management on bank performance based on bank size (small, medium and large commercial bank) in Tanzania.

Theoretical review

The study adopted shiftability theory to explain how the commercial banks can manage liquidity risk using credit investment and liquidity reserve. Moulton (1915) is the one who invented the shiftability idea. The expected income doctrine and the commercial loan theory are the two pillars upon which this theory is built. According to the shiftability theory, banks are able to shield themselves from the liquidity risks that are caused by significant withdrawals if they maintain large amounts of highly shift-enabled credit instruments in the form of liquidity reserves. The Shiftability Theory suggests that banks possess the ability to adjust their asset and liability composition strategically to manage liquidity risk effectively. In the context of our study, this theory allows for an examination of how commercial banks utilize their financial resources to navigate liquidity challenges. By considering how banks shift their holdings of assets and liabilities in response to liquidity risk, we can assess the impact of these adjustments on financial performance. This theory provides insights into the tactical decisions banks make to maintain stability while optimizing their profitability.

The study further adopted The Efficient-Structure (ES) hypothesis in explaining how relationship between performance and bank size through economies of scale, proposing that larger firms can achieve lower unit costs and higher profits. The Efficient-Structure (ES) hypothesis, proposed by Demsetz, (1973), posits that the most efficient banks achieve higher profits and market share. This hypothesis suggests that increased bank profitability results from enhancing internal efficiency and governance rather than being solely driven by market interests (Amato & Wilder, 1988). Empirical evidence supports the idea that higher profits attract depositors to banks, indicating that banks with enhanced profitability are often more efficient in their operations (Olweny & Shiphoo, 2011). The ES hypothesis is typically presented through two distinct approaches, each focusing on different aspects of efficiency. The X-Efficiency approach suggests that companies operating more efficiently gain greater market share and higher profits by reducing production costs for any given level of output (Al-Muharrami & Matthews, 2009). In contrast, the scale-efficiency approach explains the relationship through economies of scale, proposing that larger firms can achieve lower unit costs and higher profits.

On the other hand, the Market-Power hypothesis posits that a bank's profitability is primarily influenced by market-related factors. The Efficient-Structure hypothesis, however, asserts that a bank's performance is more significantly impacted by internal efficiency and managerial decisions, which are internal factors. Consequently, researchers often incorporate variables from both hypotheses into bank performance models, recognizing that a bank's profitability is influenced by a combination of internal and external factors (Olweny & Shiphoo, 2011).

Methodology

Study Design and Variables Selection.

This study employed panel data research design, using 23 commercial banks over a period of five years (2017 to 2021), focusing on peer bank groups as defined by Ernst & Young (2021). The study used secondary data extracted from annual reports of central bank as well as and Commercial banks. The selection of these commercial banks was contingent upon the availability of data within the study period and aligned with the primary objective of the research. The variables considered in the study comprised the dependent variable, Return on Assets (ROA) which also adopted by Ndoka et al., (2017), Amnim et al., (2021) and Sidhu et al., (2022) in measuring the profitability of the banks. Additionally, the independent variable consisted of the ratio of Liquid Assets to Total Assets, which assesses a bank's capacity to withstand liquidity shocks which also used by Ferrouhi, (2014), Marozva, (2015) and Y.-K. Chen et al., (2018) in measuring liquidity risk of banks.

Table 1:Skewness/Kurtosis tests for Normality

Variable	Pr (skewness)	Pr (kurtosis)	Adj chi2 (2)	Prob>chi2
LA/TA	0.1616	0.9169	2.01	0.3655
ROA	0.1623	0.4418	2.62	0.2692

The normality results from table 1 suggest that both variables have p-values greater than the significance level of 0.05, indicating that they are normally distributed. Therefore, the assumption of normality is not violated for these variables. Additionally, the joint test of normality (adj chi2(2)) shows chi-square values of 2.01 for "LA/TA" and 2.62 for "ROA" with corresponding p-values of 0.3655 and 0.2692, respectively. Since the p-values are greater than 0.05, there is no evidence to reject the null hypothesis of normality for both variables jointly.

Table 2. Harris-Tzavalis unit-root test for ROA and LA/TA

Ho: Panels contain unit roots		Number of panels = 23	
Ha: Panels are stationary		Number of periods = 5	
	statistic	z	p-value
ROA	0.0337	-4.5887	0.0000
LA/TA	0.0816	-4.1173	0.0000

The unit-root test results from table 2 suggest that Both variables have p-values less than the significance level of 0.05, indicating strong evidence against the null hypothesis (Ho) of unit roots. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that the panels are stationary. These results suggest that both ROA and LA/TA are stationary over the specified time period, indicating that they do not exhibit a unit root and are suitable for further analysis using fixed effects or random effects models.

Model estimation and Analysis

Since the analysis of the relationship at hand involved the use of panel data, fixed effect and random effect model were used to explain the relationship between the variables. In the random effects model, the underlying assumption is that the unobserved

heterogeneity, often referred to as individual-specific effects, and is not correlated with the independent variables. This suggests that these individual-specific effects are random and do not exhibit systematic relationships with the explanatory variables. In the fixed effects model, the individual-specific effects are assumed to be correlated with the independent variables. This model effectively controls for all time-invariant unobserved heterogeneity by including a separate fixed effect for each entity.

Random Effects Model

Mathematically, the random effects model can be represented as follows:

$$ROA_{it} = B_0 + B_1 \left(\frac{LA}{TA} \right)_{it} + a_i + \varepsilon_{it}$$

Where: ROA_{it} is the ROA for entity i at time t . $(LA/TA)_{it}$ are the respective independent variables for entity i at time t . β_0 is the intercept. β_1 is the coefficients for the independent variables. α_i represents the unobserved individual-specific effects. ε_{it} is the error term.

Fixed Effects Model

The fixed effects model can be represented similarly:

$$ROA_{it} = B_0 + B_1 \left(\frac{LA}{TA} \right)_{it} + \alpha_i + \varepsilon_{it}$$

In this case, α_i represents the fixed effect for entity i .

To determine the appropriate estimation method between fixed effects and random effects, the Hausman test was employed. This test involves assessing the null hypothesis, which suggests that the random effects model is more suitable. As a rule of thumb, if the probability value (P-value) is statistically significant ($P < 0.05$), we reject the null hypothesis in favor of the alternative, indicating that the random effects estimation is more appropriate. The Hausman test serves as a valuable tool in guiding the choice between fixed and random effects models in panel data analysis.

Results and Discussions

The descriptive statistics from table 3 suggest that the LA/TA variable represents the liquid asset-to-total asset ratio. On average, liquid assets account for approximately 27% of total assets in the sample, with a standard deviation of around 0.125, indicating some variability in this ratio among observations. The lowest value observed is approximately 3.2%, while the highest is around 69.6%, suggesting significant variation in the liquidity levels of the banks.

Table 3: Descriptive statistics

Variables	mean	Std.Dev	Min	Max
LA/TA	.2700562	.1252733	.0322038	.6957628
ROA	-.0387662	.3844915	-.0410031	.0641719

Regarding ROA (Return on Assets), the average return is approximately -0.039, indicating that, on average, the banks experience a slightly negative return, potentially signaling losses. The standard deviation of around 0.384 demonstrates variability in returns among observations. The lowest observed return is approximately -0.04100, suggesting significant losses in some cases, while the highest return is approximately 0.064, indicating a positive but not particularly high return.

The Hausman Specification Test

To ensure the correct specification of our econometric model, we conducted the Durbin–Wu–Hausman test with the aim of justifying the use of either fixed effects or random effects estimation. In this test, the null hypothesis posits that the random effects model is appropriate. The Hausman test results revealed probability values of 0.0058 ($P < 0.05$) and 0.0076 for medium and small commercial bank groups, respectively. This indicates that we can reject the null hypothesis in favor of the alternative, suggesting that the fixed effects model is suitable for these two groups. Conversely, for the large commercial bank group, a probability value of 0.1758 ($P > 0.05$) was obtained. This implies a failure to reject the null hypothesis, indicating that the random effects model is more appropriate for the large commercial bank group.

Additionally, a Breusch and Pagan Lagrangian multiplier test for random effects was conducted, yielding a probability value of 0.3439 ($P > 0.05$). This test suggests that random effects may not be necessary in this regression model, and a simple Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression is more appropriate for the large commercial banks group.

Estimation Models

After confirming from the Hausman test that the OLS regression was appropriate for large banks group fixed effect was appropriate for medium and small bank group the model was estimated and the results are as presented in Table 4, 5, and 6 respectively.

Table 4. Name of the table OLS Regression results for large commercial banks

ROA	Coef	Std.Err	z	P>[z]	[95% Conf.Interval]
LA/TA	.0141312	020572	0.69	0.492	-0261892 .0544515

The specific objective of the study was to estimate the relationship between liquid assets to Total asset ratio and return on asset (ROA). As observed from table 4 for large commercial banks, this ratio had a significance level of 1.4%, which indicates that it was not statistically significant in relation to the return on asset. This implies that for large commercial banks, as the ratio of liquid assets to total assets increases, their financial

performance does not show a statistically significant change. However, the direction of the relationship is positive, indicating that higher liquid asset ratios might be associated with slightly better financial performance for large commercial banks, but this relationship is not strong enough to be considered statistically significant. As a result, the practical implications of this relationship may be limited

Table 5. Fixed effects estimations result for medium commercial banks.

ROA	Coef	Std.Err	t	P>[z]	[95% Conf.Interval	
LA/TA	.1211809	.0219941	0.43	0.045	-0.242127	.0665744

The finding also indicates that large banks are not significantly affected by holding slightly higher levels of liquid assets. Lotto, (2019) states that bank efficiency is commonly improved for banks that hold liquid assets, and banks strive to increase liquid assets, improving operating efficiency. Kajola et al., (2019) point out the positive influence of bank liquidity on the profitability of 10 banks in Nigeria from 2008 to 2017. Findings from both Kajola et al, (2019) and Lotto (2019) are a bit inconsistent with findings of small and medium banks in this study. Banks with higher liquidity regenerate high income because excess liquidity allows banks to extend credit activities that increase their profitability. Bordeleau & Graham (2010) found a curvilinear relationship between holding liquid assets and a bank's profitability. According to their findings, profitability improves as banks hold some level of liquid assets. However, there is a threshold beyond which holding further liquid assets starts to diminish a bank's profitability (Chen et al., 2021).

Table 6. Fixed effects estimations result for small commercial banks.

ROA	Coef	Std.Err	t	P>[z]	[95% Conf.Interval	
LA/TA	-.4675901	.2054798	-2.28	0.046	-.9254277	-.0097525

Shiftability Theory suggests that banks adjust their asset portfolios in response to changing economic conditions, aiming to maintain stability and profitability. In this context, the finding that large banks are not significantly affected by holding slightly higher levels of liquid assets supports the idea that these banks are capable of shifting their asset composition as needed without significant impact on profitability. This suggests that large banks have the capacity to manage liquidity risk efficiently, ensuring that they can adapt to changing market conditions without sacrificing profitability.

On the other hand, as observed from table 5 medium commercial banks had a negative significance level of -12%, suggesting a weak but statistically significant relationship between liquid assets and return to asset. And from table 6 Small commercial banks had an even stronger negative significance level of -46%, indicating a more substantial and statistically significant association between liquid assets and return to asset. This means that as the ratio of liquid assets to total assets increases for medium and small commercial banks, their financial performance (as measured by the dependent variable, likely ROA) tends to decrease. This finding is consistent with the results of previous studies conducted by (Mwangi, 2014) and (Florrah, 2018). It implies that these banks might be sacrificing potential higher returns by holding excessive liquid assets, which could be used more

profitably elsewhere. Arif & Anees, (2012) and Siddik et al., (2017) show that liquidity adversely affected banking performance in developing economies between 2004 and 2014. Maintaining an excess liquidity position is costly and inefficient.

According to the Shiftability Theory, banks adjust their asset portfolios to maintain stability and profitability in response to changing economic conditions. In this case, the negative relationship suggests that medium and small commercial banks may not be efficiently managing their liquidity positions. Holding excessive liquid assets could mean missed opportunities for higher returns elsewhere in their portfolios. These banks may be overly conservative in their liquidity management, leading to lower returns on assets. This inefficient allocation of resources contrasts with the idea of efficient asset shifting proposed by the Shiftability Theory. The Efficient-Structure hypothesis posits that larger, more diversified banks tend to be more efficient in managing resources and generating returns. While the ES hypothesis generally supports the notion that larger banks are more efficient, the negative relationship found in medium and small banks could be attributed to inefficiencies in their operations. These banks may lack the scale or diversification to manage their resources optimally, leading to a negative impact on profitability when holding excessive liquid assets.

Conclusion And Recommendations

Conclusion

we can conclude that bank size does matter in the context of performance and liquidity risk management for commercial banks in Tanzania. It is generally argued that maintaining more liquid assets compared to total assets provides a certain level of risk management capability. Therefore, the study stresses that banks should establish optimal size of liquidity to maximize returns and invest excess liquidity in higher-yielding assets or where additional income can be generated without significantly increasing risk.

For medium and small commercial banks: There is a significant negative relationship between the ratio of liquid assets to total assets (LA/TA) and financial performance, measured by metrics like Return on Assets (ROA). This suggests that as these banks increase their proportion of liquid assets, their financial performance tends to decrease. It implies that they may be sacrificing potential higher returns by holding excessive liquid assets, which could be used more profitably elsewhere and highlights the importance for medium and small banks to carefully manage their liquidity positions to optimize financial performance.

For large commercial banks: The relationship between LA/TA and financial performance was found to be positive but insignificant. This suggests that for large commercial banks, the proportion of liquid assets to total assets does not have a statistically significant impact on financial performance. While holding higher levels of liquid assets may be associated with slightly better financial performance for large banks, the effect is not strong enough to be considered significant. Large banks may have reached a level of efficiency where holding slightly higher levels of liquid assets does not significantly affect their profitability. So, while bank size does play a role in performance and liquidity risk management, the nature of this relationship varies across different sizes

of commercial banks in Tanzania. Medium and small banks need to balance liquidity with profitability, while large banks may have already optimized their liquidity management practices to a level where further increases in liquid assets do not lead to significant improvements in profitability.

Implications and Recommendations

The implications of these findings for medium and small commercial banks in Tanzania are significant. Since a higher proportion of liquid assets is negatively associated with financial performance, these banks may need to carefully balance their liquidity management by establishing the optimal amount of liquid assets to be maintained. They should consider optimizing their liquid assets to a level that ensures operational stability while not exceeding the point where it negatively impacts their financial performance. This might involve improving the efficiency of their asset allocation and investment strategies.

For large commercial banks, while the relationship is not statistically significant, they should continue to monitor their liquidity management practices. It's advisable for them to maintain an appropriate level of liquid assets that aligns with regulatory requirements and operational needs. They can focus more on other factors that might impact their financial performance, such as loan quality and interest rate risk management. Overall, the findings suggest that liquidity management strategies should be tailored to the specific needs and size of the bank to optimize financial performance and ensure banks stability. Regulatory authorities may need to consider different liquidity management guidelines for medium and small commercial banks compared to large commercial banks. They can tailor these guidelines to ensure that the proportion of liquid assets is appropriate for the size and nature of the bank. This may help smaller banks avoid overcommitting to liquid assets, which can negatively impact their financial performance. Further areas of study related to the findings include examining the impact of regulatory changes on liquidity management, conducting cross-country comparisons, and analyzing the influence of macroeconomic factors, market competition, and market structure on liquidity management and financial performance can shed light on the underlying dynamics at play.

Limitations of the study

The study's focus solely on commercial banks in Tanzania limits the generalizability of its findings to other geographical regions or types of financial institutions. Banking systems and market conditions vary between countries, so the results may not be applicable to banks operating in different regulatory environments or economic contexts. The study's reliance on financial data from a specific five-year period may restrict the applicability of its findings to other timeframes. Economic conditions, regulatory frameworks, and market dynamics can change over time, potentially influencing the relationships between variables studied. Additionally, heavy reliance on financial data may overlook qualitative factors that could influence the relationships under investigation, such as management practices, regulatory changes, or market sentiment.

Areas for future research

The study's findings offer valuable insights, but further research could delve deeper into the underlying reasons for the observed relationships. Exploring factors beyond the scope of this study, such as management practices, technology adoption, and customer-centric initiatives, could provide additional insights into factors deriving better financial performance. The future studies could also focus on the issues that make bank performance to vary based on bank size. Given the fact that they operate under the same economic environment.

Abbreviations (Nomenclature)

LA/TA	Predicted value Liquid assets to total assets ratio
ROA	Return on asset
T	Time
α_i	represents the unobserved individual-specific effects
α_i	represents the fixed effect for entity i.
β_0	Is the intercept.
β_i	Coefficients for the independent variable.
ε_i	it is the error term

Author Contributions

As far as the data collection is concerned, Mr.Mwanagwa Moharuma was largely involved in preparation of checklist that was used during data collection, data collection and data cleaning before the analysis. Dr. Kembo M. Bwana was largely involved in data analysis and discussion of the findings

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References

- Ajibike, J. O., & Aremu, O. S. (2015). The impact of liquidity on Nigerian bank performance: A dynamic panel approach. *Journal of African Macroeconomic Review*, 5(2), 23–41.

- Akhtar, M. N., & Saleem, S. (2021). The impact of market discipline on charter value of commercial banks: Empirical evidence from Pakistan stock exchange. *The Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 8(4), 249–261.
- Al-Ardah, M., & Al-Okdeh, S. (2022). The effect of liquidity risk on the performance of banks: Evidence from Jordan. *Accounting*, 8(2), 217–226.
- Alim, W., Ali, A., & Metla, M. R. (2021). *The effect of liquidity risk management on financial performance of commercial banks in Pakistan*. <https://mpru.ub.uni-muenchen.de/id/eprint/112482>
- Al-Muharrami, S., & Matthews, K. (2009). Market power versus efficient-structure in Arab GCC banking. *Applied Financial Economics*, 19(18), 1487–1496.
- Alshatti, A. S. (2015). The effect of credit risk management on financial performance of the Jordanian commercial banks. *Investment Management and Financial Innovations*, 12(1), 338–345.
- Amato, L., & Wilder, R. P. (1988). Market concentration, efficiency, and antitrust policy: Demsetz revisited. *Quarterly Journal of Business and Economics*, 3–19.
- Amnim, O. E. L., Aipma, O. P. C., & Obiora, C. F. (2021). Impact of covid-19 pandemic on liquidity and profitability of firms in Nigeria. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 11(3), 1331–1344.
- Anbar, A., & Alper, D. (2011). Bank specific and macroeconomic determinants of commercial bank profitability: Empirical evidence from Turkey. *Business and Economics Research Journal*, 2(2), 139–152.
- Arif, A., & Anees, A. N. (2012). Liquidity risk and performance of banking system. *Journal of Financial Regulation and Compliance*.
- Bassey, G. E., & Moses, C. E. (2015). Bank profitability and liquidity management: A case study of selected Nigerian deposit money banks. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management*, 3(4), 1–24.
- Bordeleau, É., & Graham, C. (2010). *The impact of liquidity on bank profitability*. Bank of Canada.
- BOT. (2021). *Financial sector supervision annual Report*.
- Chen, W.-D., Chen, Y., & Huang, S.-C. (2021). Liquidity risk and bank performance during financial crises. *Journal of Financial Stability*, 56, 100906.
- Chen, Y.-K., Shen, C.-H., Kao, L., & Yeh, C.-Y. (2018). Bank liquidity risk and performance. *Review of Pacific Basin Financial Markets and Policies*, 21(01), 1850007.

- Demsetz, H. (1973). Industry Structure, Market Rivalry, and Public Policy. *The Journal of Law and Economics*, 16(1), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1086/466752>
- DeYoung, R., & Jang, K. Y. (2016). Do banks actively manage their liquidity? *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 66, 143–161.
- Ernst & Young. (2021). *Tanzania banking sector review*.
- Ferrouhi, E. M. (2014). Bank liquidity and financial performance: Evidence from Moroccan banking industry. *Verslas: Teorija Ir Praktika*, 15(4), 351–361.
- Florrah, K. (2018). *Effects of Liquidity Risk on Financial Performance of Commercial Banks in Kenya*.
- Gafrej, O., & Boujelbéne, M. (2022). The impact of performance, liquidity and credit risks on banking diversification in a context of financial stress. *International Journal of Islamic and Middle Eastern Finance and Management*, 15(1), 66–82.
- Goddard, J., Molyneux, P., & Wilson, J. O. (2004). The profitability of European banks: A cross-sectional and dynamic panel analysis. *The Manchester School*, 72(3), 363–381.
- Kajola, S. O., Sanyaolu, W. A., Alao, A., & Ojunrongbe, O. J. (2019). Liquidity and profitability dynamics: Evidence from the Nigerian banking sector. *Accounting and Taxation Review*, 3(2), 1–12.
- Kosmidou, K., Tanna, S., & Pasiouras, F. (2005). Determinants of profitability of domestic UK commercial banks: Panel evidence from the period 1995-2002. *Money Macro and Finance (MMF) Research Group Conference*, 45, 1–27.
- Kutsienyo, L. (2011). *The Determiners of Profitability of Banks in Ghana* [PhD Thesis]. Masters Dissertation, Institute of Distance Learning, Kwame Nkrumah
- Lee, J. Y., & Kim, D. (2013). Bank performance and its determinants in Korea. *Japan and the World Economy*, 27, 83–94.
- Lotto, J. (2019). Evaluation of factors influencing bank operating efficiency in Tanzanian banking sector. *Cogent Economics & Finance*, 7(1), 1664192. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23322039.2019.1664192>
- Marozva, G. (2015). Liquidity and bank performance. *International Business & Economics Research Journal (IBER)*, 14(3), 453–562.
- Muriithi, J. G., & Waweru, K. M. (2017). *Liquidity risk and financial performance of commercial banks in Kenya*.
- Mwangi, F. M. (2014). *The Effect of Liquidity Risk Management on Financial Performance Of Commercial Banks In Kenya*.

- Ndoka, S., Islami, M., & Shima, J. (2017). The impact of liquidity risk management on the performance of Albanian Commercial Banks during the period 2005-2015. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Education Research*, 3(1), 70–76.
- Olweny, T., & Shipho, T. M. (2011). Effects of banking sectoral factors on the profitability of commercial banks in Kenya. *Economics and Finance Review*, 1(5), 1–30.
- Poposka, K., & Trpkoski, M. (2013). Secondary model for bank profitability management-test on the case of Macedonian banking sector. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 4(6), 216–225.
- Sayed, S. N. (2014). Credit risk, market power and exchange rate as determinants of banks performance in Nigeria. *Journal of Business and Management*, 16(1), 35–46.
- Siaw, S. (2013). *Liquidity risk and bank profitability in Ghana* [PhD Thesis]. University of Ghana.
- Siddik, M. N. A., Kabiraj, S., & Joghee, S. (2017). Impacts of capital structure on performance of banks in a developing economy: Evidence from Bangladesh. *International Journal of Financial Studies*, 5(2), 13.
- Sidhu, A. V., Rastogi, S., Gupte, R., Rawal, A., & Agarwal, B. (2022). Net Stable Funding Ratio (NSFR) and Bank Performance: A Study of the Indian Banks. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 15(11), 527.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/jrfm15110527>
- Sufian, F., & Chong, R. R. (2008). Determinants of Bank Profitability in A Developing Economy: Empirical Evidence from The Philippines. *Asian Academy of Management Journal of Accounting & Finance*, 4(2).
- Vodová, P. (2011). *Liquidity of Czech Commercial Banks and its Determinants*. 6(5).

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